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Students' Views Studying in Arabic Preparatory Class on Distance Education During the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

Countries have taken some urgent decisions in order not to experience an irreparable loss in the field of education due to the Covid-19 pandemic that affected the world as of the end of 2019. In this process, the distance education decision was among the measures taken for the students to get through the education period with the least damage and without loss of time. Distance education tools, which were previously used at a limited level in many areas, have become widespread and used at all levels of education processes. In Turkey, distance education tools were used in all stages of education in this process and universities had to expand this education tool that they were familiar with. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the 2020-2021 academic year was carried out almost entirely with distance education tools. Due to the decision taken by the Higher Education Council (CoHE) and universities during the pandemic process, there were also students who had to take their foreign language learning with distance education tools. In this study, it is aimed to reveal the situation faced by students who had to take one year preparatory education through online programs before starting the Arabic Language Education undergraduate program. In this process, open-ended questions were asked with a semi-structured interview form to the students who continued their education. The answers given by the students to the questions posed were evaluated with descriptive analysis. While there are students who find distance education positive due to situations such as listening to lessons in a comfortable environment at home, being with the family, there are those who evaluate this process negatively due to situations such as the ineffectiveness of the lessons, the internet shortage, and the inability to take the exams in a reliable environment. Students stated that they generally see this education process negatively and that they don't want to learn a foreign language with distance education tools if an option is offered.

Keywords: Covid-19, Distance Education, Arabic Learning, Preparatory Education

1. Introduction

Distance education is a tool that enables individuals to continue their education and training without having to be in any place, and brings the educator and students together on online platforms. Distance education has been used in various fields for many years, and it is a tool for educators to come together with students and ensure the continuation of education. Distance education, which is a frequently used system for people who cannot find the opportunity for education due to the conditions of education, to benefit from the right to education, has become a system that individuals from all levels benefit from in today's world. Distance education, which has been familiar

to students especially at university level in the past years, has been known and used by everyone in recent years. Distance education, which had to be used actively due to the covid-19 pandemic, which affected the whole world for about two years, affected educators and students at all stages. Distance education tools, which were used for various reasons such as conferences, seminars, in-service training in the pre-pandemic period, were perhaps used for the first time to cover all teaching stages during the pandemic period.

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic that broke out around the world at the end of 2019, distance education tools had to be used in all stages of education in Turkey, as well as all over the world. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the field of education is one of the areas most affected by this situation. The urgent goal of countries to continue education with distance education tools has been to get through this process with the least damage. UNESCO, a total of 1.646 million students in 172 countries have been affected by the pandemic since it broke out (UNESCO, 2020). In the information shared by UNICEF, it is stated that more than one billion children in the world are at risk of falling behind in the field of education due to Covid-19, and that countries implement distance education programs to enable children to learn in this process (“Education and COVID-19”, 2020). On the other hand, UNESCO announced that many countries closed schools for a long time during the pandemic process and all countries either opened completely or continued their education partially by doing online education as the risk of the pandemic decreased (“COVID-19 impact on education”, 2022). In this process, the Ministry of National Education (2020) in Turkey, with its decision, stated that education should be continued with distance education tools in all units of education. In the information note shared by the Council of Higher Education (CoHE) in March 2020, higher education institutions decided to continue their education remotely, with the exception of applied and face-to-face education, for the programs that have been decided to be distance education due to the pandemic and which are currently being carried out with distance education (“Koronavirüs covid-19”, 2020). During the pandemic, many departments in universities continued their courses on distance education platforms. However, this situation caused students to look at education from different perspectives. In this process, due to technological opportunities, geographical location or personal reasons, it was not possible for all students to fully attend classes. This situation affected the motivation of the students in many departments and the students were generally negatively affected by the distance education process.

Sahin and Shelley (2008, p. 216) state that as long as students have the skills to use online tools during distance education and perceive distance education as a useful and flexible way of learning, communication and sharing, it will be possible for them to enjoy online education. Success in foreign language learning is directly proportional to the person's ability to make sense of what they have learned. In order to achieve this, language learning must be made meaningful for the individual (Gömleksiz, 2013, p. 651). The statements of the students that what they learned while learning a foreign language through distance education is incomplete may have resulted from the lack of an effective means of communication in this process.

Various studies have been conducted on the effectiveness of distance education in many fields. The use of distance education tools in foreign language teaching, especially during the pandemic process, reveals the necessity of working towards this. Despite the possibility of using distance education completely again due to similar situations such as the pandemic, it is important to evaluate the positive and negative aspects by conducting studies on the distance education process. Accordingly, this study was carried out in order to determine how positive or negative the process, which covers the preparatory period of Arabic language learning, was for the students. Students who had to take the Arabic preparatory period with distance education tools were asked questions with a semi-structured interview form and the answers given to the questions were analyzed by descriptive analysis method.

In the study, various questions were asked to the students about how the effectiveness of distance education in learning Arabic as a foreign language is perceived by the students. Based on the answers given by the students depending on the questions about how they went through this process, various evaluations were made and suggestions were presented.

In addition, students who had to continue their Arabic preparatory education with distance education tools in the 2020-2021 academic year had the opportunity to compare these two periods with the start of face-to-face education after the decision taken due to the decrease in the pandemic. This study provided the opportunity to evaluate the

teaching process of the students in general during the pandemic period. Students freely answered the questions posed to them. As a result, special and general evaluations were made. The general purpose of the study is to evaluate this process based on the opinions of the students who received Arabic preparatory education in the distance education process. In addition, it is to reveal the positive and negative aspects of distance education, which has to be used by students in foreign language learning.

1.1 Distance Education

Distance education is an interdisciplinary field that tries to eliminate the limitations between learning, teaching and learning resources, and uses existing technologies with a pragmatist approach to achieve this (Bozkurt, 2017, p. 87). Koçdar (2006, p. 23) states that distance education offers students the opportunity to benefit from education whenever and wherever they want, regardless of time and place. Akgül and Oran (2020, p. 17) also state that with the introduction of technology into the field of education, distance education changes the habits of people and societies, and they adapt to new opportunities in the learning process. During the pandemic that has erupted around the world in the past two years, almost all people have made an effort to fully adapt to distance education.

With the emergence of distance education, it provides the opportunity to easily access information by providing equal opportunities in education to individuals with various disabilities or individuals with different socio-economic status, who are in different geographical conditions, and the individual can access information from anywhere (Başar, Arslan, Günsel, & Akpınar, 2019, p.16). In fact, although this is an indicator of convenience and development, it has been a matter of debate whether it provides the same effect as face-to-face education. Uşun (2006, p.19-21) states that distance education provides lifelong, individual and independent learning opportunities, and besides the responsibility of learning is on the individual, it has benefits such as improving the ability of individuals to make decisions on their own in terms of access to information and entrepreneurship. However, he underlines that distance education may not be effective enough for students who do not have the habit of working and learning individually and independently.

Distance education is advantageous in that it appeals to a wide audience, eliminates physical distance, and can be adjusted according to the individual pace of the student and those who do not have the opportunity to go to school; It is also considered to be disadvantageous due to the high initial investment cost, the disruptions that may occur in technological systems, the difficulty in preparing the curriculum and the application-oriented subjects, and the lack of motivation of the students who do not have the ability to work individually (Altıparmak, Kurt ve Kapıdere, 2011, s. 321).

Erfidan (2019, p.8-9) stated that distance education is carried out in two different ways as synchronous and asynchronous, and that it is a classroom system in which the teacher and the student come together in various ways in synchronous education platforms; expresses that asynchronous learning platforms are a system in which the student can start and finish education whenever the student wants by acting independently of the teacher. In the asynchronous model, the necessary materials are loaded into the system and can be accessed at any time.

The advantages and disadvantages of asynchronous learning environments can be listed as follows (Midkiff & DaSilva, 2000; cited in Erfidan, 2019, p. 9-10):

Advantages of Asynchronous Distance Education Model:

- Eliminates the barrier of time and space.
- Anyone who wants to have the opportunity to participate in the training.
- Education gains an international qualification as an identity.
- The student can participate in the course and the content as he wishes.
- The participation of shy students in classes increases.

Disadvantages of Asynchronous Distance Education Model:

- Creates a virtual and dispersed student community.
- The courses are not suitable for practical application.
- There is external dependency in exams that require a supervisor.
- It can create an isolated effect on students.

- Immediate feedback is not possible.

1.2 The Purpose of the Study

Arslan, Ari and Kanat (2021, p.193) stated that it was decided to suspend face-to-face education in schools in Turkey with the thought that the student population might increase the contagiousness of the pandemic to higher levels, and that the necessity of switching to distance education has arisen due to the fact that approximately 25 million students in Turkey are affected by this situation. Başar et al. (2019, p. 17) underlines that the attitude towards distance education is directly proportional to the efficiency, success and learning quality of the individual during education. They also state that it is very important to raise awareness about the functionality of distance education, as well as to improve the existing perception of distance education in individuals in a positive way. Due to the pandemic in the past education period, almost all educational institutions had to prefer distance education instead of face-to-face education. In this process, students who encountered distance education for the first time encountered various problems in distance education, where they had to continue their education. The aim of this study is to reveal the problems faced by the students who had to study during the preparatory period before starting the undergraduate program in the field of Arabic language education during the pandemic period and to evaluate the process in line with the answers they gave. Thus, students' perspectives on learning Arabic with distance education tools were revealed. As a result of this study, which was carried out in order to reveal the experiences of students during the preparatory period, which is an important period for students in Arabic language learning, while they were using distance education tools, the effectiveness of distance education in language learning was evaluated in a way. In addition, one of the aims of the study is to make suggestions for language teaching with distance education as a result of the study. The problem statement of the research was determined as follows. "What are the views of the students who had to take the Arabic preparatory period with the distance education tool during the Covid-19 process on distance education?" In this context, answers to the following questions were generally sought in the study:

1. Are distance education tools sufficient for learning a foreign language in general, Arabic in particular?
2. What are the positive and negative aspects of distance education in learning Arabic?
3. How did learning Arabic through distance education affect students?
4. What are the difficulties encountered during distance education in Arabic learning?

Evaluating the answers given to the questions posed to the students in the study and making general conclusions enabled the deficiencies of this process to be revealed. In addition, it is thought that such studies are important in terms of providing an idea about which aspects should be taken into account in a similar situation that may occur in the future. Balaman and Tiryaki (2021, p. 59) state that the evaluation of the teachers' views on distance education during the pandemic period will contribute to the development of distance education activities to be carried out in the following periods and to eliminate the deficiencies.

2. Method

2.1 The Model of the Research

This research, in which students' opinions are evaluated, is in the phenomenology model, one of the qualitative research designs. The main purpose of qualitative research is to focus on the experiences and perspectives of the participants and to reveal their perceptions and experiences (Tekindal and Uğuz Arsu, 2020, p. 158). Sart (2015, p. 73) states that the basic question is what is the meaning, structure and essence of the lived experience of a person or a phenomenon that is the subject of research in phenomenology. In the study, questions were asked to the students with a semi-structured interview form about distance education. Allowing the students to freely answer the questions posed to the students with the semi-structured interview form ensures that the data of the study are objective. The answers given to the questions were analyzed by descriptive analysis and evaluated under certain headings, presented graphically and interpreted. In the study, the opinions of the students who personally experienced the distance education process were consulted. As a result, the positive and negative aspects of this process, the situations that need to be developed and the students' thoughts on which distance education would prefer face-to-face education were revealed.

2.2 Participant Characteristics

The study group was formed with the purposeful sampling method. One of the characteristics of qualitative studies is to work on a small-scale sample with distinctive features (Snape and Spencer 2003, p.4-5 cited in Buran, 2015, p. 43). In phenomenological studies, data sources are individuals or groups that carry the phenomenon that the research focuses on and can express or reflect this phenomenon (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak Kılıç, Akgün, Karadeniz, & Demirel, 2014, p. 20). The study group consists of 22 students who had to take Arabic preparatory education remotely at a state university in Turkey in the 2020-2021 academic year. The criterion for determining the study group is that the students receive their Arabic preparatory education through distance education. Before the study, the questions prepared on google.forms were sent to 35 students and they were asked to answer the questions voluntarily. Demographic information of the students participating in the study is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic information of students.

Variables	Category	F	%
Gender	Girl	18	81,8%
	Male	4	18,2%
Place	Village	3	13,6%
	District	5	22,7%
	City	15	68,2%

81.8% of the participants in the study are female and 18.2% are male students. Considering the place where the students live, which is an important situation for benefiting from distance education as a technical infrastructure, 13.6% stated that they live in the village, 22.7% in the district and 68.2% in the city center.

2.3 Data Collection Tool and Analysis

The questions prepared by taking expert opinion were sent to the students who took the preparatory period with the distance education tool through the google.forms link and the volunteers were asked to be answered. In qualitative research, data obtained from interview forms can be collected both face-to-face and offline. The semi-structured interview form is the form that allows the participants to answer the questions prepared within the framework of a topic and the data is reached from the interview held to collect information about the subject. Within the scope of the study, the data obtained from the semi-structured interview form were analyzed by descriptive analysis method. Baltacı (2019, p. 379) states that the purpose of descriptive analysis is to bring together the data collected as a result of interviews and observations with the reader in an organized and interpreted way. The answers given by the students were classified on the basis of questions and quotations were included to reflect the students' views. The data are presented descriptively. In the study, the answers given by the students to the questions were evaluated and a general evaluation was given with numerical information in the graph and the results were analyzed by interpreting. The interview form was initially composed of 13 questions. Then, depending on the opinions of the field experts, 1 question was removed and 4 questions were asked by combining them with other questions. In this context, the following questions were asked to the students:

1. What are the problems you have faced in distance education during the preparatory education?
2. What are your views on the efficiency of remote preparatory education?
3. What are your views on the effectiveness of homework assignments given during the distance education process?
4. What do you think about the reliability of the exams held during distance education?
5. Would you prefer if distance education was given again after face-to-face education?
6. Can you indicate the positive aspects of distance education for you?
7. Do you think distance education is a useful system for learning a foreign language?
8. In what way do you think the distance education process affects your Arabic learning?

3. Results

As a result of the descriptive analysis, the data were graphically coded and interpreted. In the study, the quantitative results of the data obtained from the answers given by the students to the questions were given in the graph, and then quotations from the answers of the students were also included. The questions and answers directed to the students are as follows:

1. What are the problems you have faced in distance education during the preparatory education?

Graphic 1: Problems Encountered During Distance Education

The students stated that they mostly experienced problems related to internet problems during distance education with a rate of 41%. The motivation of the students to the lessons was negatively affected due to the reasons arising from the internet speed or the disconnection during the lesson. Students stated that they had problems reconnecting to the course due to the internet interruption. Secondly, 23% of the students stated that they had problems focusing on the lessons in distance education. In this case, it is possible that a productive course period has not been spent. 14% of the students stated that they had a lack of technology. Students who do not have sufficient technological devices in any distance education period may face the problem of not being able to follow the lessons. 13% of the students stated that they had problems related to the lecturer during this period and that they could not communicate well with the lecturers. This situation shows that students experience problems during communication due to similar reasons such as internet interruption during the distance education process. 9% of the students stated that they did not face any problems. Some of the answers given by the students to this question are as follows:

S3: "There was a problem when the internet was cut off in the live lesson or there was no sound due to weak internet."

S5: "Continuous interruptions in the lessons caused the efficiency of the lessons to remain at a much lower level than it should have been."

S7: "Technology was not enough and therefore there was a problem in understanding the lesson."

S9: "Internet access, home environment, difficulties in understanding lessons."

2. What are your views on the efficiency of remote preparatory education?

Graphic 2: Efficiency of Distance Education

Although 36% of the students stated that distance education was efficient for them, 64% of them stated that it was inefficient. This shows that the majority of the students participating in the study were not satisfied with this process. Even though some students state that the lessons are efficient, they say that they think of this efficiency because “it is easy to attend the lesson.” The main aim is to achieve the generally targeted learning outcomes in the curriculum. However, the fact that this is the opinion of the majority about the inefficiency of distance education shows that the targeted gains were not achieved in this period. It seems very difficult for students who cannot gain the proficiency to study on their own to make this process effective. Some of the students' answers are as follows:

S1: “I think that I got efficiency because the course records are registered in the system. However, the efficiency of contacting the teacher and asking questions seemed a little low. Because there was no obligation to attend the classes during the lesson.”

S16: “It was not efficient, I had difficulty in understanding the subjects.”

S18: “I had difficulty in understanding the subjects.”

3. What are your views on the adequacy of the homework given during the distance education process?

Graphic 3: Adequacy of Homework During Distance Education

When students evaluate the homework given during the preparatory education quantitatively, 77% of them think that they are insufficient and 23% think that they are sufficient. However, in order to reach more objective information on this subject, the homework they gave and the feedback they received during that period can be asked to the lecturers in another study. Because some of the students who answered made evaluations according to the courses.

S5: “Homework in some courses was quite sufficient, in others it was not.”

S7: “Assignments were insufficient.”

4. What do you think about the reliability of the exams held during distance education?

Graphic 4: Reliability of Exams

Three different variables emerged regarding the reliability of the exams. While 32% of the students stated that the exams were reliable, 54% stated that they were not reliable. 14% of them, namely 3 students, emphasized that this situation depends on the student. Some students' answers are as follows:

S3: "Of course it is open to abuse, but I think that those who want to cheat can find a way even when they are face to face."

S5: "No, it is not reliable at all, how can students who have not attended the course even once get high grades?"

S18: "It was not reliable."

S20: "There was no security. It was not even known that the student who took the exam was himself."

When the answers of the students are evaluated, it is understood that the students do not find the exams very reliable during the distance education. For this purpose, different systems such as camera tracking from another device can be developed during the exam. However, since there is no obligation to open the camera during the lessons during the preparation period, even if the camera is on during the exam, it may not be understood whether the student is the student taking the lesson. It is obvious that a versatile control mechanism should be established in online exams. Otherwise, it will be very difficult to ensure security in online exams.

5. Would you prefer if distance education was given again after face-to-face education?

Graphic 5: Preferring Distance Education to Face-to-face Education

The majority of the students stated that they would never prefer distance education again if they were given the opportunity to choose. One student stated that both face-to-face education and distance education should be at the same time. However, some courses are already taking place online. Field courses are conducted face to face. Some of the students' answers to this question are as follows:

S3: "I wouldn't prefer it because when it comes to distance education, I can hardly understand the lessons."

S5: "No, I would not prefer it. Because I wasn't getting any efficiency."

S6: "Of course, distance education is better in terms of comfort. It would be very useful if the lessons were attended regularly and homework was done. I don't want distance education for only one reason, the reliability of the exams."

S7: "No, I would not prefer it, because I get more efficiency from face-to-face education."

S21: "No, I would not prefer it. Face to face is a more effective system. It is very important to adapt in a period such as preparatory education, which is basic education, and to evaluate the education you have received and to be in the same environment with the teacher who teaches at the same time."

Students stated that they would not prefer distance education because they get more efficiency from face-to-face education. It is understood that the presence of students in foreign language learning and their active participation in the lesson affect learning positively. In addition, when the answers of the students are analyzed, it is thought that the motivation for the lessons in face-to-face education will be high.

6. Can you tell us the positive aspects of distance education for you?

Graphic 6: Positive Aspects of Distance Education

It is noteworthy that 32% of the students found distance education positive in terms of providing the opportunity to listen to lectures comfortably in their home environment. However, there are also those who say that they find this process completely negative at the same rate. In addition, 23% of the students stated that distance education has a positive economic aspect. In addition, there were those who saw this process positively, as it enabled them to be intertwined with technology tools. One student stated that it is positive that the exams are online.

S2: "I became interested in technology."

S6: "I could listen to lectures in a more comfortable environment."

S10: "I was taking lessons at my house in a nice environment every season."

S18: "There was no positive aspect."

S22: "It was positive for me economically."

7. Do you think distance education is a useful system for learning a foreign language?

Graphic 7: Foreign Language Learning with Distance Education

73% of the students stated that they found it useless to learn a foreign language with distance education tools. 18% of students think that learning a language through distance education is useful. However, those who think that this situation is beneficial stated that they think so because they have the opportunity to listen to the lectures again. Two of the students stated that foreign language learning depends on the person, even by distance education. In other words, they stated that personal effort is the most important point in success in any way. As in all other subjects, it is thought that individuals with self-study competence will progress in foreign language learning.

S3: "It was useful because the language demands it again. Thanks to the lecture recordings, we could watch the lectures over and over again."

S9: "It is a useless system because the practical ear saturation gained while face-to-face in the lesson is not the same as in distance education."

S10: "No, it is definitely not useful. Learning face-to-face is more beautiful and effective."

S22: "It depends on the effort of the person. Of course, face-to-face teaching is more efficient as we can communicate with the teacher. Learning a foreign language from a distance is something that requires more effort."

The fact that most of the students want to be in the same environment with the lecturer while learning a foreign language shows the importance of being interactive in language learning. Some students were not able to take part in the interactive process during the course because they acted with the idea that I would listen to the lecture later during the distance education process, so they stated that this process was ineffective.

8. How do you think the distance education process affects your Arabic learning?

Graphic 8: The Effect of Distance Education on Arabic Learning

77% of the students, that is the majority of them, stated that their learning of Arabic through distance education was negatively affected. It is thought that this may be due to the lack of obligation to attend classes during the pandemic and the lack of motivation they experience. It is thought that it would be successful if the study process was carried out in a disciplined way by continuing the lessons during the education process. It is thought that 23% of the students who think that it has a positive effect spend this process actively and give importance to the subject of attending classes.

S1: "I took the preparatory period with distance education and it was a very busy period for me. I spent a lot of time understanding the lessons thoroughly. I think I can learn Arabic well up to a certain level."

S11: "My Arabic learning was negatively affected."

S22: "It did not affect positively in terms of speaking skill. But it was useful in terms of paragraph, text translation and grammar."

The students thought that they were more active in the classroom environment in lessons such as verbal communication skills and stated that the process was negative in terms of similar lessons. Despite this, they stated that their Arabic learning was negatively affected in general. It can be deduced that learning Arabic as a foreign language has been a negative process for students due to the pandemic.

4. Discussion and Suggestions

Distance education tools, which are widely used almost all over the world during the pandemic process, were most actively used in the field of education. Programs used as distance education tools such as Zoom, Microsoft teams, moodle, adobe connect have strengthened the infrastructure due to the pandemic. However, various problems were encountered in this process. Students who continue their education at universities have encountered various problems in organizing this process. In addition to the technological and infrastructural shortcomings, they have mostly failed to pass the process efficiently by experiencing adaptation difficulties in distance education. This negative effect was less for students with self-study efficacy. However, for those who continued their learning process with distance education for the first time, a negative process was experienced. Kuyucu (2021, p. 91) states that, based on the students' opinions, the rate of those who think that the traditional campus will be replaced by the digital campus in the future is quite high. This shows that some of the students adapt quickly to the distance education system. However, it still does not seem possible to claim that this can happen for all departments in the

university. It is thought that it will take time for this to happen, especially in departments where direct application-oriented courses take place.

As a result of the study, although the students find distance education positive in some aspects such as continuing their education with the family and more economically, they think that it is negative in terms of foreign language learning. Because they emphasized the necessity of effective communication in foreign language learning. They stated that this would be more effective if the lecturer and the student were in the same environment. Students who state that they have difficulties in adaptation in the lessons during the preparatory education think that the positive effects of learning Arabic face to face will be more. They also emphasized that the reliability of the exams held during distance education is low. It is understood that students spend the distance education process with low motivation. In this case, assuming that there is a direct relationship between motivation and learning, it seems difficult to state that distance education can be successful without motivation. To the question 'about motivation and attendance to classes' directed to students who took courses through distance education during the undergraduate period, the students generally stated that they attended the courses with low motivation or did not attend the courses because there was no obligation to attend (Şanverdi, 2022, p.170).

Distance education tools have been used for many years, especially in higher education institutions. However, due to the pandemic, such widespread use at every stage of education has been experienced for the first time. Therefore, it was possible to encounter many problems in this process. As a result of the study, some suggestions can be made for the distance education process:

Despite the possibility of a similar situation to be experienced again, trainings containing detailed information for lecturers and students should be given in the context of distance education tools.

In order to avoid technical problems in the distance education process, teams that can intervene quickly should be formed.

Distance education courses should be organized in a way that ensures active interaction between students and teachers. In addition, the synchronous continuation of the courses and the planning of the attendance requirement will ensure a more effective learning process.

In order for distance education to be useful enough, students should have gained the ability to work on their own at all stages. Otherwise, it should not be forgotten that incomplete learning will be faced.

The continuity of studies that will increase the motivation of students and lecturers in the distance education process should be ensured. It should not be forgotten that the readiness of the students is important in distance education. In particular, students should be informed and studies on the importance of self-study competence. In addition, useful and effective homework should be given to students during distance education. These homeworks will increase the student's focus on the lessons.

Studies evaluating distance education covering many fields should be carried out. Especially during the pandemic process, detailed analyzes should be made by taking the opinions of the students who continue their education in various fields. The reports resulting from these analyzes should be submitted to the necessary units and evaluated by them. In addition, these authorized units should take improvement decisions regarding distance education based on the reports.

Workshops where the pandemic process is evaluated in various fields, especially in the field of education, should be organized and the decisions taken as a result of the workshop should be presented as a report.

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